

Validation, Measurement and Optimization of Floating Wind Energy

Lessons learned from the VAMOS project in collaboration with the FLOATEOLE project

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1 Introduction

A good understanding of floating offshore wind turbines is essential to decrease the uncertainties and risks – and thus the costs – of this very promising technology. VAMOS project addresses this challenge with a large-scale measurement campaign and a validation study. The knowledge gained will be used directly for the design of an improved turbine controller to enhance the dynamic behavior and reduce loads. In the long term, this will allow for lighter weight substructure and cheaper turbine designs.

The main objective of VAMOS was to close knowledge gaps in the measurement and simulation of floating offshore wind energy system for commercial use. The partners University of Stuttgart, Hamburg University of Technology and engineering consultant sowento collaborated with French prototype Floatgen at the SEM-REV test site for a period of 48 months. The project covered full-scale measurements, numerical modeling, control and optimization of a floating offshore wind energy system. The dynamic behavior of the floating wind turbine prototype was reproduced by numerical models of different levels of detail. A nacelle Lidar system was installed on the prototype to obtain the power curve and the wake measurements as well as a scanning Lidar was deployed on a boat near the Floatgen by Centrale Nantes in the collaborating FLOATEOLE project. The nacelle-mounted Lidar was used to validate methods to obtain the power curve. The wake measurements, on the other side, were planned to be used to validate aerodynamic models, which can reproduce the wake behind the turbine.

2 Symbols and abbreviations

FOWT	Floating offshore wind turbine
<i>pan</i> MARE	<u>p</u> anel Code for <u>M</u> aritime <u>A</u> pplications and <u>R</u> esearch
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging

3 Load measurements

Within the VAMOS project, an additional load measurement campaign was not carried out. The load measurements were provided by BW Ideol extracted from previously installed sensors on the FOWT system. The sensors of interest for the validation of the simulation model were located at tower top, tower bottom and blade root. Since the measurement systems were not installed in this project, it was not possible to perform an uncertainty quantification study. Instead, a plausibility/feasibility analysis was performed to ensure the quality of the measurements.

Blade loads

Blade loads were measured by fiber optic sensors at 1m from the root of each blade. The direct measurement data was extracted, synchronized, and strain values were calculated. Temperature correction was then applied and blade and edge bending moments were calculated. They were later calibrated based on scale and offset coefficients derived from a regular blade calibration process. During the measurement campaign in VAMOS, another blade calibration process was performed. After the calibration, blade root moments were compared to each other to verify the blades against each other. Differences indicating a decay in the post-calibration coefficients were found. Thus, measurements based on the most recent calibration are used as a reference, and blade load measurements prior to that calibration are recalibrated with an offset.

Tower loads

Similar to blade sensors, the data were extracted and strains were converted in the reference tower frame. Then, bending moments were calculated excluding the outliers. Due to the fault in temperature sensors, the temperature correction could not be carried out, thus comparison of average bending moments was not possible. Moreover, the 10-minute availability of tower moments was much lower compared to blade moments. As a result, a large scale statistical comparison of the tower loads was not possible. As a recommendation, future measurement campaigns should start after up to date calibration of load sensors and regular maintenance of sensors when possible.

Load measurements for the purpose of validation of wind turbine load simulations are typically based on the IEC 61400-13 standard. Here, measured quantities, database requirements, and methods for calibration, verification, and evaluation as well as uncertainty calculations are defined to allow load comparisons of the measurements results with simulation data. In case of FOWT, wind and structural loads are accompanied by waves, currents and mooring line tensions as external forces, acting on the floater and turbine body. Hence, for validation of FOWT extensions and modifications to the measurement standard will be required in the future. These are in particular:

- Additional measurement quantities of external and internal forces: wave and ocean measurements, mooring line tensions, floater motion.
- Additional load quantities to be evaluated, e.g., tower tension (traction/compression) in addition to bending and torsion.

- Inclusion of nacelle-based lidar or floating lidar (or new alternatives, instead of impractical offshore masts) for appropriate wind and turbulence measurements.
- Adapted procedures for load quantity calibrations, which in its classic form require very rare low wave and wind conditions.
- New definitions of measurement load cases.
- Definition of suitable coordinate systems and coordinate transformations.
- Extended uncertainty calculations, e.g., for coordinate-transformed quantities.

Lessons learned in the VAMOS project, which may contribute to the FOWT load measurement standardization are:

- High quality inertia measurement units (IMU) systems are required in tower top (or nacelle) and tower base, providing valuable information on forces (accelerations, motions) and allow precise coordinate transformations. Accuracy, frequency range and sampling rates must be selected with respect to the expected motions and accelerations.
- A wave measurement buoy in approx. 1 km distance (Floatgen case) is too far away, the load case cannot be defined with sufficient accuracy. So, it should be positioned as close as possible to the floater.
- Database completeness criteria, currently based on a wind speed and turbulence matrix, cannot be applied, because ocean conditions are not included. Since motion and turbulence are acting in a similar way on the turbine, acceleration and wind speed could be convenient to bin the data for evaluations or to define measurement load cases. However, this has not been tested within the VAMOS project.
- VAMOS has shown that nacelle lidar is applicable also for load measurements if advanced wind field reconstruction methods and data post-processing are applied. The necessity of accurately measuring turbulence (as in the classic load measurement) may be reduced, if
 - load cases are defined based on alternative quantities (see previous item),
 - rotors are getting larger, causing turbulence to have less impact on turbine loads.
- Due to a larger variety of external conditions (wind and waves), load measurement campaigns will typically take longer than onshore or with fixed foundation. A measurement campaign duration of minimum 6 - 12 months is a good estimate for planning.
- Environmental conditions for the fatigue database (e.g. DEL statistics) to be compared should be defined based on the available measurement database rather than on a fixed simulation database, unless the environmental conditions can be predicted very accurate for the test site.

- For load validation of extreme conditions, the highest loads captured during the measurement campaigns should be defined as “field extreme load cases”, to be reproduced by simulations. These should be evaluated in addition to triggerable transient load cases like emergency stop.
- Special care must be paid to repeating load calibrations, since with the larger variety of external conditions signal drifts are more difficult to detect. A recommendation would be to implement an automatic trigger in the test turbine to repeat yaw sweeps or special rotor idling tests, as soon as wind and wave conditions are suitable (very low). This data can additionally be used to verify temperature compensation effectiveness.

VAMOS did not investigate FOWT effects on the measurement uncertainty of the load quantities. Also, no data was available for mooring line tensions.

The variety of floater types is an obstacle to standardization, also in load measurements. Different types of floaters may induce completely different load patterns on the same turbine type. Hence, a load measurement can only be valid for a single floater / turbine type combination and may require design specific additional quantities or load cases to be measured. These are typically defined during the earlier certification stages. This also implies that some lessons-learned from VAMOS may not be applicable for other floater types.

4 Power curve measurements with a nacelle-based lidar on a FOWT

The accurate assessment of power performance of FOWTs is crucial for the economic viability of the floating wind industry, which relies heavily on dependable wind speed measurements. In VAMOS project, the feasibility of measuring the power curve of a FOWT utilizing nacelle-based lidar technology is examined. Over the course of a five-month measurement campaign, a nacelle-based lidar system was installed atop the 2MW Floatgen demonstrator. Wind speed estimations derived from the lidar measurements were verified against a nacelle-based sonic anemometer measurements, and then employed for power curve analysis, assessing the suitability of nacelle-based lidar for such applications.

Installation, operation and maintenance of a nacelle-based lidar on a FOWT

Determining the optimal placement for the lidar system proved to be a more difficult task than initially anticipated. Installation of the lidar along the centreline of the rotor shaft, positioned at the front of the nacelle was not possible due to constraints imposed by the structural design of the nacelle roof. Consequently, a considerable amount of time was devoted to identifying an alternative placement, necessitating extensive deliberations and consensus. This process involved identifying the exclusion zones on the nacelle roof, analysing the remaining viable positions, and assessing the percentage of beam blockage.

The installation of additional mounting plates for the lidar on the nacelle before installing the lidar proved to be highly advantageous. This approach facilitated a swifter installation of the tripod and optical head (OH), reducing the overall time required for this task by at least one full day. However, the alignment process presented unexpected challenges. The primary difficulty arose from the turbine's movement, rendering the inclinometer of the OH ineffective for achieving precise alignment. Consequently, an alternative approach was employed, utilizing a dataset spanning ten minutes and calculating the average values of tilt/pitch and roll movement to guide the alignment process. Through iterative steps, it was possible to progressively reduce the mean pitch and roll to nearly 0°. Subsequent long-term analysis of the data demonstrated the relative accuracy of this method, despite the utilization of a comparatively brief duration of averaged data. It is important to note that this alignment method is valid only under specific conditions, such as minimal floater movement, favourable weather conditions with negligible wind speed and significant wave height (i.e. significant wave heights lower than 1m).

In order to monitor the lidar operation, it is advantageous to include a remote hardware reboot option. In the event of a software failure, it is essential to enable a reboot process that can be initiated externally, avoiding direct access to the lidar system. As this was missing in the VAMOS project, it is imperative to address this issue for future campaigns. Thorough documentation of every operation facilitated seamless transitions between different personnel involved. The utilization of photos and drawings proved particularly effective in planning modifications and conducting component-related tasks. Although it was not feasible to employ materials completely impervious to the harsh environmental conditions, regular monitoring of these issues and undertaking necessary maintenance,

renewal, and repairs were imperative in preventing major failures and keeping the sensitive equipment safe.

Verification of the nacelle-based lidar measurements with a nacelle-based sonic anemometer and power curve measurements

The nacelle-based lidar measurements were used for wind field reconstruction, including a threshold filter for signal-to-noise ratio, an availability filter, and a hard target filter for the one-hertz measurements of radial wind speeds[1]. The quality of the measurement, quantified by the linear correlation and mean square error of ten-minute averages of the rotor area averaged wind speed and the hub height wind speed, was compared to the measurements from the nacelle-mounted sonic anemometer. A time-stamping error was later discovered in the dataset and corrected. This led to increased correlation of the two devices and less difference between the resulting power performance assessments. The correlation of the rotor-averaged wind speed estimates from lidar and sonic wind speed measurements yielded a high coefficient of correlation. Consequently, the nacelle-based lidar provided a reasonable wind speed estimate and a similar power curve to sonic measurements. This indicates that nacelle-based lidars can be qualified to be used for such an application on a floating offshore wind turbine.

It is also possible to analyse the power curve of a floating turbine as a function of fore-aft acceleration standard deviation. This allows the excitations of turbulence and wave induced motions to be combined into a single parameter to represent the power curve. The difference between power performance under different excitations are presented in [1]. Uncertainty quantification is of great importance for the evaluation of wind measurements using lidars, since errors in wind measurements can affect various aspects, such as the estimation of turbine performance. To address this issue for nacelle-based lidar on FOWTs, the measurement and reconstruction of wind field characteristics can be mathematically modelled. Subsequently, the sensitivity of the mathematical model to changes in the parameters involved can be determined. In this case, these parameters are the six degrees of freedom of the floating offshore wind turbine. However, in an experimental measurement campaign on a floating turbine, it is not possible to quantify uncertainties without reference measurements (i.e. stationary met-mast, motion-corrected scanning lidar measurements). Therefore, the use of multiple and/or more advanced measurement systems to reduce the uncertainties associated with future measurement campaigns is important.

To overcome the issue of missing reference measurements for the nacelle lidar a simulation-based study on the quantification of motion-induced uncertainties in lidar wind speed measurements was conducted and published in [2]. Authors used analytical model, employing the guide for the expression of uncertainty in measurements (GUM) methodology and a numerical lidar simulation for the quantification of uncertainties. They found that the uncertainty of lidar wind speed estimates is mainly caused by the fore-aft motion of the lidar, and therefore, is heavily dependent on the amplitude and the frequency of the pitch motion. This approach was utilized in VAMOS project for the nacelle-based lidar measurement campaign set-up.

5 Wake measurements of a FOWT using a scanning lidar

Despite strong effort supplied by the ECN team in the last years to develop a marinised embedded and autonomous scanning LiDAR to be installed on the Floatgen platform during several months, this goal had not been achieved within VAMOS project duration. Alternatively, a first offshore measurement campaign with the stabilised scanning LiDAR has been completed. This measuring device, the result of technological development in the laboratory, was deployed to characterise the wake of a floating wind turbine, FLOATGEN, installed on the SEM-REV test site. After initial onshore testing, several months of preparation proved necessary to design, assemble and validate the stabilised LiDAR. In this set-up, the measuring instrument (250 kg) is held horizontally by a stabilising platform to enable it to acquire data under optimum conditions, despite the movements of its floating support, be it boat or platform. In September 2022, the stabilised LiDAR was taken on board a ship for a first 3-day offshore campaign: Measurements were acquired around the Cardinaux lighthouse - also instrumented with wind sensors by the LHEEA - in order to verify the system, and then on the SEM-REV offshore test site, off the coast of Le Croisic in the vicinity of BW Ideol's floating wind turbine FLOATGEN, which was installed on site in 2018.

The test campaign was successful. The stabilised LiDAR was able to acquire its first data sets and the stabilisation device proved its value in this complex environment. The objective of these offshore measurements was to acquire data on offshore wind resources and to be able to characterise the wake of a floating wind turbine. Understanding and modelling these wakes is essential to quantify the possible interactions between several wind turbines and thus improve the production of offshore wind turbines. Data that is key for today's deployment of floating wind farms.

Facing the extremely challenging and costly experimental setup and procedure, it is obvious that measurement time is rare and expensive. Therefore, the careful development and precise planning of measurement load cases is of major importance to ensure a successful measurement campaign. For this purpose, a wake LiDAR simulator based on a free-vortex-wake method has been developed by TUHH. The LiDAR simulator is an add-on to the panel method panMARE, which is a simulation framework for FOWT motions and loads. In this way, a prediction of the measured flow field in the line of sight of the LiDAR is possible. The most relevant environmental conditions, the FOWT motion and the LiDAR measuring characteristic are considered by the simulator. Finally, the LiDAR simulator can also be used to compare measurement and simulation of the near-wake field.

Technical challenges and solutions associated with the wake LiDAR measurement campaign.

The scanning LiDAR: The scanning LiDAR VCube 100S is a product of Vaisala (ex-Leosphere). It can measure wind speed along the line of sight (cross section or around 10cm of diameter) from 50m up to 3km distance, with a space resolution of 25m, minimum. The data accumulation is performed during the scanning and its standard duration is 0.5 to 1s.

The scanning LiDAR can measure in any directions in an upper half-sphere, but the captured velocity is the projection of the wind speed along the laser beam (line of sight). It is therefore

recommended to align the line of sight as much as possible with the streamwise direction. Some scan scenarios (as Plane Position Indicator PPI) enable the reconstruction of the global wind direction and a 2D plane of local horizontal wind speed. This device is dedicated to the measurement of atmospheric flows, where the velocity gradients are characterised by large space and time scales. The measurement of the wind turbine wakes, characterised by stronger and more localized velocity gradients, is possible but some limitations need to be clearly stated: the line of sight should be aligned as much as possible with the space direction of minimum velocity gradient (here the streamwise direction). The velocity field in the near-wake, which presents strong modifications in short distance and contains tip vortices, cannot be captured reliably, as the velocity variations will be filtered according to the space resolution and accumulation time. On the other hand, this filtering effect can be predicted by the LiDAR simulator. This opens the possibility to compare isolated characteristics of the near-wake, like the distance between tip vortices and its modulation due to the floating motion of the FOWT.

The scanning LiDAR is normally planned to operate in fixed conditions. Its use in marine conditions needs to be carefully planned. Compared to the wake dimensions, the floater translations had been considered as minor. Knowing that the optimal distance of measurement is 500m-1km, the floater rotations had been considered as major sources of measurement errors (relative velocity and modification of the measurement location).

Marinisation

- The stabilisation platform: It has been chosen to compensate only two DoFs (pitch and roll) and to correct through data processing the other DoFs (surge, sway, heave and yaw). Its specifications were based on simulations of the Floatgen floater Response Amplitude Operators (RAO). The residual motions are measured with an Inertial Measurement Unit.
- The device position and orientation are monitored with a GPS system.
- All instrumentation is synchronised to the same clock (GPS clock)
- The data acquisition and storage needs to be designed according to the volume of data generation and the frequency of data collection (every day, week, month?). Its robustness and the associated costs need to be balanced.
- Encapsulation: It was chosen to encapsulate the overall system into a container, with an opening on the top of it to extract the scanning head from the container for measurement campaigns. A protection system of the LiDAR in case of harsh sea conditions needs to be designed. The transition piece between the container and the floater platform also needs to be carefully designed, must fulfil the safety regulations and must be certified by the floater owner.
- Remote system: the marinised and stabilized scanning LiDAR is supposed to operate autonomously during several months. All user actions need to be performed remotely. Physical user actions need to be highly limited since it means the necessity to travel on place by ship.

Installation location

- On Floatgen platform: The possibility to fix the stabilised scanning LiDAR on the Floatgen platform allows to link the observer reference framework with the wake generator, i.e. the wind turbine. The motions of a wind turbine floater are at a lower

frequency range than a ship or a buoy, the (hardware) compensations or (software) corrections are easier to address. The stabilization platform had been designed to compensate such low-frequency pitch and roll motions.

- Ship: The measurement campaign was carried out on the ship MINIBEX, which is equipped of a dynamic positioning (DP) system. This functionality was essential to ensure that the observer reference framework (positioning and orientation) was not varying too much during each scan. Even if the stabilisation platform had been designed for wind turbine floater motions, its behavior in ship conditions was considered as satisfying, on the basis of the preliminary data processing.

On the other hand, the decoupling of the frameworks of reference of the floating wind turbine (which moves) and the stabilised scanning LiDAR, makes the data processing and the result's interpretation much more difficult. For instance, depending on the scanning speed, the wind turbine can experience one cycle of low-frequency surge during one scan on a 45° sector.

Seasonal constraints: the long-term installation must be planned in spring or summer to avoid the seasons when harsh meteorological conditions could prevent from marine operations. On the other hand, the seasons of interest are fall and winter. Ideally, if one want to measure 6 months, August or September are the best time slots for installation.

- Duration of preliminary campaign: If only a proof a concept or preliminary testing of all the technological bricks are foreseen, a measurement campaign of a few days is enough. The data collection along a few hours, enable to check the measurement scenarios, the motion compensation efficiency, the data acquisition and synchronization, the measurement correction according to the residual motions. The possibility to test the measurement system in the vicinity of a met mast as reference provides a good opportunity to assess the measurement accuracy and correction.
- Duration of systematic campaign: Since the atmospheric flow properties depend on wind direction, wind speed, thermal stability, sea state, and the wake properties depend additionally on wind turbine operation, the boundary conditions of this complex phenomenon are varying all the time. Additionally, wind and waves are non-deterministic, leading to the need for statistical processing. The classification of data according to all these parameters is essential to categorise the boundary conditions and perform statistical analyses. Considering that statistics of at least 100 (ideally 400) independent samples are needed to obtain an accurate ensemble average, the right trade-off need to be found between the granularity of the configurations and the number of samples that fall into each configuration. A measurement campaign of at least one month per type of scenario (far-wake, near-wake, nacelle-mounted-like measurement of wind resource, etc.) should be applied.

Wake LiDAR simulator for FOWT

A LiDAR simulator for the prediction of platform-based single-line and LiDAR scanners mounted on FOWTs has been developed to allow for an a priori evaluation of measurement load-cases. The FOWT simulation method panMARE is utilised to predict the platform

motion as well as the flow field in the wake. Based on the platform motion and the scanning pattern, the position of the LiDAR beam is evaluated at every time step, such that the time-dependent flow field in the line-of-sight can be extracted from the simulations. A post processing is applied to the extracted velocities: First, a temporal average over the data acquisition time is computed. Second, the beam is subdivided into the gates corresponding to the LiDAR configuration. Third, a convolution with a Gaussian weight function in space is applied to model the LiDAR measurement characteristics. As a result, a precise estimation of the LiDAR velocity measurements with comparable time and space filtering can be achieved. The estimation includes the influence of the environmental conditions on the FOWT motion, including the LiDAR and its beam, as well as on the wind and wake field. In addition, the influence of the tower top motion on the wake is captured.

Critical measurement load cases can be evaluated a priori using the wake LiDAR simulator. For example, the expectable yaw motions of the turbine and the platform as well as their influence on the wake displacement for an exemplary measurement period can be estimated. To achieve this, an exemplary wave and wind field in time domain is generated from statistical data in order to model a realistic scenario. The information gathered from the estimated LiDAR measurements can be used to either define the limiting environmental conditions for a measurement load case (i.e. maximum wind direction change) or to adapt the scanning mode, spatial or temporal discretisation to extend the range of acceptable environmental conditions.

A near-wake scanning load case was developed with the aid of the LiDAR simulator. As discussed above, the limited spatial and temporal discretisation of the scanning LiDAR makes it impossible to resolve the flow field of the near-wake with a sufficient accuracy in time domain. Especially the time discretisation is a limiting factor for the analysis of the floating motion's influence on the near-wake. However, the LiDAR simulator revealed that certain flow details may be captured with unconventional LiDAR scanning setups: A possible setup would be a single beam with increased the sampling frequency to a maximum (e.g. 10Hz), which points in a vertical direction and penetrates the wake of the wind turbine near its centre line. In this case, the tip vortices, which are convected downstream with the wind cross the LiDAR beam and induce a significant signature to the line-of-sight velocity. In a post processing, it would be possible to determine the time between two tip vortices passing the beam and to compare their strength. Both quantities are highly sensitive to the tower top surge motion of the wind turbine. Therefore, the influence of the floating motion on the tip vortex development could be characterised using the scanning LiDAR.

The wake LiDAR simulator can also be utilised to validate the underlying free-vortex-wake method. With panMARE's ability to import the measured platform motion and wind velocity into the simulation, it is possible to reproduce the measured scenario with sufficient detail. Therefore, different near- and mid-wake scanning patterns can be compared to the free-vortex-wake simulations.

6 Modelling, verification and validation of a FOWT

Aerodynamic modelling of the Floatgen FOWT

A number of different modelling approaches to compute the aerodynamic loads on the Floatgen wind turbine have been extensively compared. From low to high fidelity models, these are: SLOW[3], a reduced order model for controller development, AeroDyn (NREL), a classical BEMT method and *panMARE*, a first order panel method. The methods under investigation follow different approaches to model the flow around the rotor blades. While *panMARE* explicitly models the flow around the blades and calculates the three-dimensional wake structure (free wake), AeroDyn relies on an azimuthally averaged induction model, which estimates the actual inflow velocity and angle of attack at every blade section. The classical BEMT is inherently quasi-steady and therefore unable to model the influence of transient changes of the blade flow. Therefore, a dynamic inflow model (based on Oye, see Snel[4]) and an unsteady aerodynamic airfoil model (based on Beddoes and Leishman[5]) are used to introduce corrections for the BEMT method in order to be able to consider transient aerodynamic effects. While the dynamic inflow model accounts for the fact that the induction of the wake can only change gradually, the unsteady aerodynamic airfoil model predicts the reaction of the lift force to a transient change of the local angle of attack based on two-dimensional thin airfoil theory. Both are implemented in AeroDyn and are also used in other BEMT codes. The SLOW model is developed to run extremely fast and therefore relies on predefined coefficients for rotor torque and thrust dependence on the rotational speed, blade pitch angle and rotor effective wind speed. In consequence, the behaviour of the SLOW model is quasi-steady.

The primary aim of the comparison study was to identify modelling discrepancies during transient aerodynamic situations typical for a FOWT. However, it became clear in the early stage of the project that there are also quasi-stationary differences between the models. This is due to the fundamentally different modelling strategies. BEMT methods rely on empirical lift and drag coefficients while a panel method directly models the blade pressure distributions. As a consequence, it is crucial to characterize such quasi-steady modelling differences in order to be able to distinguish these from the transient effects. It turned out that another key point for the identification of discrepancies in the modelling of transient phenomena is a careful definition of the load cases and comparison metrics in order to exclude the influence of the quasi-stationary differences. To achieve this, a number of different dynamic disturbances like pitch step, gust and surge motion were simulated with various durations but the same magnitude. In all load cases, the variation of the tip speed ratio (TSR) was kept the same, while the characteristic period of this change was varied. As a result, the transient part of the load response to the disturbances becomes visible when comparing the cases with short and long duration.

It was found that the BEMT method with the dynamic corrections is able to model the transient aerodynamic phenomena occurring during a pitch step, a gust and a periodic variation of the rotational speed qualitatively. However, there are significant quantitative differences in the rotor loads due to the transient effects especially for the high-frequent variation of the rotational speed of the rotor. The response to a surge motion contained only minor transient parts, which led to discrepancies of around 5 to 10% between the

models. However, it was observed that the BEMT model with unsteady aerodynamic corrections predicted a reduction of the torque and thrust amplitudes, while the panel method computed a slight increase (see [6]). Even though the influence of transient phenomena on the load oscillation of the surging wind turbine rotor is limited, it has to be noted that the unsteady corrections for BEMT seem to miss a significant physical effect. Recent investigations of a number of different rotors revealed the presence of the returning wake effect [7], which is most likely the effect that causes the above described differences between the panel method and the BEMT simulations.

A specific feature of this analysis is the small size of the rotor, which has a diameter of 80m. In this special case, the wake reduced frequency, which is a measure for the unsteadiness of changes in the wake of a wind turbine, is relatively small. Therefore, it is straight forward that the overall impact of transient phenomena during surge motion can be expected to be limited. The wake reduced frequency f_w is defined as follows:

$$f_w = \frac{f_m D}{v}.$$

where f_m , D and v denote the motion frequency, rotor diameter and average inflow wind speed. However, for modern wind turbines with significantly larger rotors, the rotor reduced frequency and consequently the unsteadiness of the wake rises notably. Therefore, it is crucial to keep in mind the limited ability of the unsteady correction methods available for BEMT to model the transient aerodynamic phenomena during a surge motion. With larger rotors, the observed underestimation of the load amplitudes may become more significant at low wave periods. As a deeper analysis of these transient phenomena predicted by the panel method and their influence on large rotors is still ongoing, it is recommended to evaluate BEMT simulation results with care. First indications on this topic can be found in [7]. Generally, the rotor reduced frequency may serve as an indication for the presence of transient aerodynamic phenomena: In the investigations during the VAMOS project, notable discrepancies between the panel method and the BEMT method with unsteady corrections occurred at a rotor reduced frequency of 1 and higher. On this basis, critical environmental conditions (i.e. wave periods and wind speeds), where BEMT simulation results may be inaccurate, can be identified for a certain FOWT design. However, it is likely that the rotor reduced frequency is not the only relevant dimensionless number that may indicate the presence of transient aerodynamic effects.

In future investigations, the observed effect of transient phenomena on the load response of a rotor in surge motion at high rotor reduced frequencies need to be verified with other high fidelity modelling approaches. In case the presence of these phenomena can be verified, their influence on the loads needs to be characterised for large rotors, so that a clear indication of the expected modelling error can be given. However, as such analysis are very rare at the present state, designers may keep in mind that the uncertainty of BEMT methods with common unsteady corrections may potentially rise with the rotor reduced frequency. In the worst case, torque and thrust amplitudes induced by the platform motion may be incorrect.

Hydrodynamic modelling of the Floatgen FOWT

The motion behaviour of the entire FOWT has a significant influence on the loads. Therefore, predicting the motion as accurately as possible is essential for efficient FOWT

design and should be possible early in the design phase. For accurate motion simulation, it is important to consider the interactions of all system load components, including the loads resulting from the rotor, the mooring system and the platform.

Panel methods are a widely used approach in this field. They are capable of determining the forces on large structures based on potential flow theory, which implies wave-induced forces and radiation effects. Within panel methods, there are two main approaches, the frequency-domain and the time-domain methods. The former are characterized by a particularly efficient calculation that considers the problem as linearized. Thus, it is solvable in the frequency domain and the results can be described by a set of coefficients for damping and added mass. For the transfer of simulation results in the time domain, only the coefficients are used, while no time dependent solution of the flow field around the platform is carried out. In the time domain approach, the flow field is solved in each time step and the solution includes the instantaneous position of the platform and wave elevation which involves highly nonlinear effects within the potential flow solution. The pressure on the hull surface is evaluated using Bernoulli's equation and then integrated to estimate the hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces. Added mass effects are automatically included in the time-dependent hull pressure

A unique feature of the Floatgen platform by BW IDEOL is the moonpool inside the barge-type structure. It is a vertical opening through the platform and the water inside has a specific motion characteristic that dampens the platform heave motion at certain frequencies. Sloshing and piston modes are the main cause of water motion [8] and a challenging subject for modelling methods.

During the VAMOS project, numerical models of the platform were set up in four different simulation tools. Two of them are frequency-base methods, an OrcaFlex model from BW Ideol and an OpenFAST/HydroDyn model by USTUTT. OrcaFlex [9] model has already been calibrated based on tank tests and turned out to be conservative with respect to measurements [10], as in some cases larger motion amplitudes or loads occurred in the simulation in comparison to the measurements. OrcaFlex is coupled with OpenFAST to include the turbine loads. The OpenFAST[11] model by USTUTT is based on the same frequency dependent hydrodynamic coefficients as used in OrcaFlex in order to minimize modelling differences. These hydrodynamic coefficients are verified by an Ansys AQWA model of the platform. It is recommended to use an external lid to suppress standing waves within the structure, which otherwise could lead to large jumps of coefficients in irregular frequencies. However, this approach using an external lid on the moonpool surface in Ansys AQWA could not be implemented as it requires additional calibration parameters [12], which requires specific tank-tests. Therefore, designers should be aware of these potential non-physical effects.

The third model from TUHH is based on the time-domain method *parMARE* [13,14], see Figure 1. Besides the different hydrodynamic modelling, an important difference should be mentioned: In the method, a rigid body assumption is applied, which means that structural deformations such as the bending of blades or towers are not taken into account. All above described methods include a dynamic lumped mass mooring model, with the dynamic stiffness of the nylon ropes.

Figure 1 Numerical grid of the free surface applied in the panMARE model.[15]

The fourth model is the SLOW model developed by USTUTT. It uses linearized hydrodynamic coefficients and quasi-static mooring line forces for fast calculation during the controller design and optimization. However, difficulties arise in linearization due to non-linearity introduced by the moonpool platform. This can be resolved by fine-tuning the linearization of hydrodynamic coefficients and added hydrodynamic properties.

Model verification

A detailed code-to-code verification was performed including steady state position, free decay and excitation in waves. The results of the models agree well in pitch but have some differences in the heave motion. The results obtained from OrcaFlex and OpenFAST show only small deviations, and mainly in damping. This can be explained by the different treatment of the irregular waves. The panMARE results show larger differences in response amplitudes and natural frequency (see RAO in Figure 2). This may be a result of different modelling of the moonpool dynamics, which heavily affect the vertical motion of the platform.

Figure 2 RAO calculated at different wave heights over a normalized wave period.[15]

Special aspects of the hydrodynamic modelling with a panel method

The time-domain panel code *panMARE* solves the three-dimensional flow field based on a discretisation of the platform hull and the free surface around it, see Figure 1 . A number of modifications have been implemented to overcome some of the limitations of the pure potential method such calculating the impact of green water on deck or breaking waves. The free board of the platform was extended to increase the stability of the free surface solver in high waves where green water can flood the deck. This extension was only virtual and has no influence on the platform mass or centre of gravity. The pressure forces on the virtual extension was neglected, as only ambient pressure can act on the platform deck. A damping factor is applied on the free surface panels inside the moonpool to include viscous effects at its entrance based on the approach of Faltinsen and Timokha[16]. The damping and stabilising parameters of the free surface strongly influenced the resulting heave motion. They were set to be in a reasonable range, but due to the lack of experimental data, they could not be validated.

Validation using a hybrid simulation approach

Validating the models based on measurement data was a valuable opportunity within the frame of the research project. The experimental results provided by BW Ideol included high resolution data in time domain of the platform motions, load cells on tower and blades as well as turbine operation. Unfortunately, the wave elevation was only available for a wave buoy in a distance of about one kilometre away and it was not possible to reproduce the exact wave elevation at the platform location. The missing wave elevation did not allow for a direct validation of the coupled *panMARE* model in time domain. Therefore, a hybrid simulation approach was introduced, where the measured platform motion and wind field is applied on the simulation model. Following this approach, a constrained simulation was achieved, where the turbine and tower experienced the measured motion and environmental conditions.

Figure 3 Validation of the hybrid simulation with wind speed below rated turbine operation.[15]

An example is shown in Figure 3, where the turbine is operating below rated wind speed. The tower top bending moments agree very well and capture the time history of the measurement. Deviations occur in some periods, mostly regarding the peak height. Similar behaviour can be seen for the rotor speed and torque, with slightly larger variances. They can be caused by the fact that the generated wind field does not capture all details of the wind experienced during the measurement period. Overall, the hybrid simulation approach allows for an accurate validation of the turbine and tower loads in time domain without the inaccuracies of wave elevation and platform modelling.

Full validation of the simulation models

The initial and fundamental step in creating the necessary inputs for simulations is the definition of environmental characteristics. By accurately understanding and specifying the environmental conditions, the impact of these conditions on the system being studied can be effectively modelled and analysed. Methodologies to determine wind and wave characteristics, which is discussed in the LIFES50+[17], were adopted. By leveraging the insights and findings from previous research, the efficiency and effectiveness of the work were significantly enhanced. An accurate representation of wind and wave conditions are required to establish a joint probability distribution of wind speed, significant wave height and peak wave period. This distribution provided a comprehensive understanding of the interaction between wind and wave characteristics. By considering the joint probabilities, valuable insights were gained into the combined effects of these environmental factors, enabling the development of more reliable comparison studies. An important lesson was learned regarding the importance of deriving appropriate bin sizes for the parameters used in the joint probability distribution. This is FOWT design dependent and can be derived by conducting a sensitivity study of the simulation model under various operational conditions as discussed in [17]. Through systematic variation of the parameters and observation of their impact on the model, the optimal bin sizes that effectively captured the range of environmental characteristics were identified. The sensitivity study on the 2MW wind turbine revealed the feasible bin sizes that were needed. Thus, for the validation study, a range of 30 degrees of the wind direction is chosen where large variety of the wind speed and significant wave height was apparent. Most probable bins from the joint probability distribution of mean wind speed, significant wave height and peak wave period were simulated. Wave direction was dominant towards the coast, thus, only the dominant sector of 30 degrees was considered. Vertical wind shear and turbulence intensity were not included in the joint probability distribution as they greatly limited the amount of data per bin. Instead, the resulting measurements are reported as an indication of parameter space for these two parameters.

During the analysis of the motions, a crucial discovery was made regarding the accuracy of the model. It became apparent that a recalibration of the added linear and quadratic damping coefficients, as well as the Morison drag coefficient, was necessary. The initial model parameters provided by BW-Ideol was found to overestimate the motions, leading to an overestimation of loads on the tower and blades. Recognizing the need for recalibration is vital to ensure accurate simulations. To achieve the desired recalibration, it was determined that the adjustments should be made as a function of peak wave periods by comparing it to the motion response in frequency domain. This approach allowed for a more precise adjustment of the coefficients, resulting in improved accuracy in predicting

motions and loads. By studying the behaviour and performance of full-scale demonstrators, designers can gather valuable information and observations that can inform design adjustments. These adjustments have the potential to reduce costs by avoiding overly conservative designs while still ensuring safe and reliable performance.

During the validation study, a crucial lesson learned was the significance of considering highly transient conditions, such as grid failure. These conditions can induce large dynamics in the system due to the rapid reduction of thrust on the rotor. By acknowledging and accounting for these transient scenarios, a more comprehensive understanding of the system's behaviour can be obtained. While highly transient conditions were considered in the validation study; additional cases, such as start-up and shut-down, should also be taken into account. These operational scenarios can introduce unique dynamics and challenges that impact the system's performance. However, in this particular project, it was not possible to command the simulation controller specifically for these cases, limiting the extent of analysis and validation.

All in all, through accurate modelling and definition of environmental characteristics and leveraging existing knowledge made in other projects, it was possible to ensure a meaningful comparison study for validation of medium-fidelity FOWT simulation model. Identifying the need for platform damping coefficient calibration based on full-scale motions and loads helps avoid overestimation and provide valuable insights for design adjustments and cost reduction. Acknowledging and considering highly transient conditions, such as grid failure, in the analysis contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of system behaviour. In order to decrease the uncertainties with respect to waves in time domain, high resolution wave height measurements would be very valuable.

Future publications are expected to showcase the scientific papers resulting from the verification and validation efforts of the Floatgen in VAMOS project.

7 Lidar-assisted Control of Floating Wind Turbines

A detailed recommended practices report has been published.

The development of floating wind turbines has created new opportunities for designing and operating wind turbines. However, these floating systems face challenges due to increased motion and interactions with wind, waves, current, and mooring lines. The report focuses on lidar-assisted control (LAC) techniques for floating wind turbines and provides recommended practices.

The report compares four different wind field reconstruction methods with different motion compensation considerations through aero-elastic simulations. It highlights the importance of translational velocity compensation and accurate inertial measurement units in achieving desired control behavior for floating turbines.

Four lidar-assisted feedforward control techniques for floating turbines are introduced. For baseline lidar-assisted controllers and multivariable feedback controllers, the inclusion of notch filtering near the platform's natural frequency is crucial. Two advanced techniques, lidar-assisted multivariable feedforward control and lidar-assisted model predictive control, are discussed, highlighting their benefits and associated challenges. The report also provides detailed steps for implementing and validating lidar-assisted control for floating turbines.

The benefits of lidar-assisted control are demonstrated through aero-elastic simulations, showing a reduction in tower base bending load and fairlead tension load compared to a benchmark multivariable feedback controller.

The report gives an overview of lidar-assisted control, its history, and its applications. It explains the measurement problem faced by lidar systems in estimating the rotor effective wind speed and the control problem of addressing the "negative damping" effect in floating wind turbines. Various controller design approaches, including detuned proportional-integral (PI) controllers and multivariable controllers, are discussed.

Finally, it mentions that as wind loads become increasingly dominant for large floating wind turbines, advanced lidar-assisted control solutions hold promise.

The full report can be found online here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8031738>

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